

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№4 (2)

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2026

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 2026-yil, aprel.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldix'o'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Faxridinov Zafarjon Faxridin o'g'li, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi HIJQKD boshqarma boshlig'i
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Anijon viloyati prokurorining o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi IJQK Departamentining Namangan viloyati boshqarmasi boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamxonovna, bank-moliya akademiyasi professori, DSc., professor.
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjayevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Fakhriddinov Zafarjon Fakhriddin ogli, Head of the DCEC under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Rep. of Uzb.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Prosecutor of Anijan Region
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the Namangan Regional Department of the Department of Internal Affairs of Rep. of Uzb.
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamkhanovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA “AKT XIZMATLARI” TUSHUNCHASI VA ULARNING EKSPORT SALOHİYATI.....	14
Shermatov Sherzod Xotamovich RAQAMLI MARKETING STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ORQALI KORXONALAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARI	20
Amonov Mirzohid Tuymuratovich, Xodjajev Anvar Rasulovich TIJORAT BANKLARINING BYUDJET MABLAG‘LARI HISOBIGA MOLİYALASHTIRILADIGAN LOYIHALARDAGI ISHTIROKINI KUCHAYTIRISH MEXANIZMLARI	26
Maxmudov Rahimjon Hamid o‘g‘li KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING STRATEGIK YO‘NALISHLARI.....	33
Shakirova Gulbaxor Sharipdjanovna YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O‘TISHDA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR TAHLILI VA UNI O‘ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA QO‘LLASH IMKONIYATLARI	38
Ne‘matova Mavsuma, Xolmamatov Diyorbek ВЛИЯНИЕ НАЛОГООБЛОЖЕНИЯ НА ИНВЕСТИЦИОННУЮ АКТИВНОСТЬ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	43
Буранова Лола Вахобовна ФИНТЕХ-ЭКОСИСТЕМА КАК ФАКТОР ИНКЛЮЗИВНОГО И УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА: СТРУКТУРНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ	54
Эшмуротов Дониёр Ихтиёр угли ZAMONAVIY MARKETING KONSEPSIYALARI ASOSIDA XIZMATLAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINING USLUBIY JIHATLARI.....	60
Ostonaqulova Gulsaraxon Matyoqub qizi, Fayzullayeva Zamira Alijonovna XIZMAT KO‘RSATISH KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA‘MINLASHDA SERVIS XAVFSIZLIGI INDEKSI: SAMARQAND VILOYATI MISOLIDA	64
Shodmanova Zubayda Ubaydullayevna QURILISH FAOLIYATI SOHALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING ILG‘OR XORIJIY TAJRIBALARI	
Xusanov Kamoliddin Xolmamat o‘g‘li INSON KAPITALI VA KADRLAR SALOHİYATINI BOSHQARISHNING NAZARIY KONSEPSIYALARI	73
Abdullo Sohobov O‘ZBEKISTONDA URBANIZATSIYA JARAYONLARI JADALLASHUVI VA UNING HUDUDIY XUSUSIYATLARI	84
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich KORXONALAR MOLİYAVIY HOLATINI MOLİYAVIY HISOBOTNING XALQARO STANDARTLARI (MHXS) ASOSIDA BAHOLASHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	91
Xamidov Javoxir Shavkat o‘g‘li BIZNES JARAYONLARINI MONITORING QILISH TIZIMINING HOZIRGI HOLATI TAHLILI.....	95
Dadajonova Madina Ravshan qizi O‘ZBEKISTON VA XORIJIY MAMLAKATLARDA BENEFITSIAR MULKDOR KONSEPSIYASINI QO‘LLASHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI	100
Ochilov Farhod Malikovich O‘ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O‘TISHNING MAKROIQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH (GDP, BANDLIK VA INVESTITSIYALAR KESIMIDA).....	106
Hayitov Jamshid Xolboyevich	

INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIKKA TA'SIR QILUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI.....	111
Mamatqulova Hafiza Bahodir qizi IPOTEKA BOZORI MUAMMOLARINING EMPERIK TAHLILI VA ULARNI BARTARAF ETISH STRATEGIYALARI.....	118
Olokulova Feruza Mansurovna, Safarova Dilrabo Baxriddin qizi MILLIY IQTISODIYOT RAQOBATIDA NAZARIY VA AMALIY QARASHLAR.....	122
Karimova Iroda Abdusattarovna KORPORATIV BANK XIZMATLARIGA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR HAMDA ZAMONAVIY BIZNES MODELLARNI JORIY ETISHNING STRATEGIK YO'NALISHLARI.....	128
Qurbonov Abror Abdullayevich GREEN ECONOMY DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN AND INDONESIA: A COMPARATIVE STUDY.....	133
Ibrokhimova Iroda Ikromjon Kizi. Askolani. Javliyev Nuriddin Bektemir o'g'li AHOLI BANDLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA REKRUTING AGENTLIKLARINING O'RNI.....	142
Sherkulova Nodirabegim Baxordin qizi ФАКТОРЫ ТЕКУЧЕСТИ КАДРОВ И МЕХАНИЗМЫ УДЕРЖАНИЯ ПЕРСОНАЛА В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	148
Джураева Гузаль Шавкатовна BUDJET DAROMADLARI TARKIBIDAGI SOLIQLARNING ULUSHINI BOSHQARISH.....	156
Abduraxmonova Gulmira Sobir qizi RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA AVTOSERVIS SHOHOVCHALARINI BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	161
Marqayev Xurshid Aliqulovich THE ECONOMIC NATURE OF HUMAN CAPITAL AND ITS RECOGNITION IN ACCOUNTING AS AN OBJECT OF ECONOMIC ANALYSIS.....	165
Zafar Qodirov Abdivaxobovich O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA JARAYONLARINING SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH.....	170
Ibragimov G'ayrat Ablaqulovich. Tursunov Ozod Matlubovich Shukurova Nilufar Qahramonova IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE SERVICES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	175
Mirzaev Kulmamat Djanzakovich NODAVLAT NOTIJORAT TASHKILOTLARI MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI BAHOLASHDA INTEGRAL KO'RSATKICHLAR TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	179
Aliyev Arslon Salom o'g'li A STUDY ON THE COLLABORATIVE MECHANISM OF DIGITAL ARCHIVES GOVERNANCE AND TALENT GOVERNANCE: AN ANALYSIS BASED ON JOB COMPETENCY, PERFORMANCE EVALUATION, AND ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS.....	184
Wang Biao USTAMA ISHLAB CHIQUARISH XARAJATLARINING MAZMUNI VA UNI XALQARO STANDARTLARGA MUVOFIQ TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	190
Tashnazarova Dilfuza Samiddinovna INTEGRATSIYA SAMARADORLIGINI O'LCHASHNING METODOLOGIK MODELI VA INDIKATORLAR TIZIMI.....	195
Aliqulov Abbas Baxtiyor o'g'li XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	202
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	

MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTLAR AUDITINI XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	207
Elomonov Dadaxon Ozodullayevich	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARIDA IQTISODIY RESURLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH YO'LLARI	213
L.S. Azimova	
THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IFRS AND FINANCIAL REPORTING	218
Tojiboyev Abdullajon Kamoliddin o'g'li	
PAXTA-TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATIDA DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIKNING HUQUQIY ASOSLARI	223
Abdullayev Hamidulla Abdug'ani o'g'li	
TURIZM KORXONALARIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATINI OSHIRISH ORQALI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI KUCHAYTIRISHNING ZAMONAVIY BOSHQARUV MEXANIZMLARI	227
Ergasheva Zarifa Baxtiyarovna	
CHO'L-YAYLOV CHORVACHILIGI MAJMUASI RIVOJLANTIRISH	232
Nurmanov Sherzod Xujayarovich	
KREDITORLAR REYTINGINI MASHINAVIY O'QITISHGA ASOSLANGAN BASHORATLASH ALGORITMLARI	237
Beknazarov Ulug'bek Zafar o'g'li	
MIKROIQTISODIYOTDA ISTE'MOLCHILAR XULQ-ATVORI VA TALAB SHAKLLANISHI OMILLARI	242
Raximov Azizbek Saliyevich	
OLIY TA'LIMNI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING ILG'OR XORIJIY TAJRIBASI: AQSH MISOLIDA.....	246
Kurbanov Baxodir Negmatullayevich	
O'ZBEKISTON TURIZM INDUSTRIYASINI BOSHQARISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLARNI JORIY ETISH USULLARI	250
Ashurova Shaxnoza Almasovna	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA OMMAVIY AXBOROT VOSITALARI KORXONALARINING MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	257
Sharipova Shahlo Istamovna	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	262
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	
XIZMATLAR SOHASIDA MIJOZ QONIQISHINI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARI: QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASI MISOLIDA	278
Aqsungul Usenova Tenel qizi, Qoraqalpoq davlat universiteti	
Dawletmuratov Adilbay Mirzaboyevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA QANDOLAT MAHSULOTLARI BOZORINING SHAKLLANISHI VA RIVOJLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI.....	283
Azlarova Munira Muhammad-Amin qizi	
TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORINI SHAKLLANTIRISH, RIVOJLANTIRISH VA KO'RSATKICHLARINI O'RGANISH.....	289
Bozorova Madina Raxmat qizi	
IMPROVING SERVICE QUALITY MONITORING IN SERVICE ENTERPRISES BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES	294
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	
KREDITLASH MEXANIZMINING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA UNING TARIXIY RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI	299
Ortiqov Husan Usmonaliyevich	

O'ZBEKISTONDA QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR BOZORI MUAMMOLARI VA RIVOJLANISH YO'NALISHLARI	304
Abdusalomov Ozodbek Baxtiyor o'g'li XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA SERVIS XAVFSIZLIGI INDEKSI: SAMARQAND VILOYATI MISOLIDA	311
Shodmanova Zubayda Ubaydullayevna O'ZBEKISTONDA EKSPORTNI OSHIRISHDA AKT RIVOJLANISHINING O'RNI.....	315
Sadriddinov Ulug'bek Jaloliddin o'g'li QURILISH FAOLIYATI SOHALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING ILG'OR XORIJIY TAJRIBALARI.....	322
Xusanov Kamoliddin Xolmamat o'g'li INSON KAPITALI VA KADRLAR SALOHİYATINI BOSHQARISHNING NAZARIY KONSEPSIYALARI	326
Abdullo Sohibov SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARI ASOSIDA TIJORAT BANKLARIDA RISK-MENEJMENT SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH	331
Davronov Sanjar Ziyotovich SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARI ASOSIDA BOSHQARUV QARORLARINI QABUL QILISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	336
Ashrapova Noilaxon Niyazxanovna ISHLAB CHIQRISH KORXONALARINI BOSHQARISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING XORIJIY TAJRIBASI TAHLILI VA UNGA ILMIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	340
Ochilov Baxtiyor Muminjonovich THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IFRS AND FINANCIAL REPORTING.....	346
Tojiboyev Abdullajon Kamoliddin ugli SIRKULYAR IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH: MUAMMOLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	351
Astanakulov Olim Tashtemirovich Muxammad Id Balbaa (Muhammad Eid Balbaa) Habibe Elif Kutlugun (Habibe Elif Kutlugun) GLOBAL IQLIM O'ZGARISHI FONIDA EKOLOGIK SIYOSAT VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH STRATEGIYALARI.....	357
Xamzayev Abdushukur Xudoyqulovich INTERNATIONAL MARKETING STRATEGIES FOR UZBEKISTAN'S TEXTILE INDUSTRY: CHALLENGES, OPPORTUNITIES, AND ECONOMETRIC EVIDENCE.....	362
Aziz Kurbanovich Abdullaev Sarvarbek Allayev Erkin ugli Shavkat Asrolovich Ruziev DIRECTIONS FOR TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES	369
Mirzaev Kulmamat Djanzakovich TEMIR YO'L TRANSPORTIDA SOLIQQA TORTISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI TAHLILI ("O'ZBEKISTON TEMIR YO'LLARI" AJ MISOLIDA).....	373
Barotov Baxtiyor Vaxobovich CHIQUINDILARNI QAYTA ISHLASHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHDAGI O'RNI	377
Muxitdinova Kamola Alisherovna TRANSPORT LOGISTIKASIDA TAVAKKALCHILIKLARNI SUG'URTALASH: O'ZBEKISTON VA AQSH TAJRIBASI ASOSIDA TAQQOSIY TAHLIL.....	381
Jabborov Islom Xusan o'g'li YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY SALOHİYATINI BARQAROR BOSHQARISH.....	385
Xayrullayev Shaxram Yunus o'g'li	

RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA SERVIS KORXONALARIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATI BOSHQARUVINING ZAMONAVIY MODELLARI	392
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	
BIZNES JARAYONLARI MONITORINGI SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH MEZONLARI VA KO'RSATKICHLARI.....	398
Dadajonova Madina Ravshan qizi	
SIRKULAR IQTISODIYOT KONSEPSIYASINI AMALGA OSHIRISHNI BAHOLASH KO'RSATKICHLARINI (INDIKATORLARINI) SHAKLLANTIRISH.....	403
Sharifxo'jayeva Xonzodaxon A'lo qizi	
TURIZM QISHLOQLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH MEZONLARI VA INDIKATORLARI TIZIMI	408
Xudaynazarova Dilorom	
NODAVLAT OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA MOLIYAVIY BOSHQARUV VA BOSHQARUV HISOB TIZIMINING AMALIYOTI: MUAMMOLAR VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	416
Xojiboyev Muxiddin Shodimuxamedovich	
DAVLAT XARIDLARI JARAYONIDA XAVFLARNI IDENTIFIKATSIYA QILISH, TASNIFLASH VA RISKKA ASOSLANGAN ICHKI AUDITNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	421
Meliboyev Askar Eshmuratovich	
DEVELOPING GARMENT MANUFACTURING STRATEGY IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	426
Mahbuba Rahmonova	
Feruza Mansurovna Ollokulova	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASI QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA INVESTITSIYA SIYOSATINING IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI.....	430
Bakhit Mambetnazarov	
Atabek Tureev	
SOLIQ TUSHUMLARI VA MAJBURIY AJRATMALARNING DAVLAT MOLIYASIDAGI O'RNI: 2020-2025 YILLAR TAHLILI VA ISTIQBOLI.....	434
Olimov Shukurulla Dilshodjon o'g'li	
ФАКТОРЫ ТЕКУЧЕСТИ КАДРОВ И МЕХАНИЗМЫ УДЕРЖАНИЯ ПЕРСОНАЛА В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	439
Джураева Гузаль Шавкатовна	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA KICHIK KORXONALAR IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	447
Mamirov Zamir Uzoq o'g'li	
XORIJIIY TO'G'RIDAN-TO'G'RI INVESTITSIYALARNI JALB ETISHDA O'ZBEKISTON TAJRIBASI: MUAMMOLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	453
Xatamov Nurbek Ochildiyevich	
DAVLAT BYUDJETI XARAJATLARI HISOB VA TAHLILINING AMALDAGI TIZIMI	458
Ostonokulov Azamat Abdurkarimovich	
Tursinbaev Gafur Jolmurzaevich	
MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTLAR AUDITINI XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	464
Elomonov Dadaxon Ozodullayevich	
СТРАХОВАНИЕ КАК ИНСТРУМЕНТ СНИЖЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫХ ПОТЕРЬ ОТ НЕПРЕДВИДЕННЫХ РИСКОВ, ОКАЗЫВАЮЩИХ ВЛИЯНИЕ НА ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКУЮ ПРИБЫЛЬ (ДОХОД).....	470
Азимжон Мелиев Муродулло угли	
A STUDY ON THE COLLABORATIVE MECHANISM OF DIGITAL ARCHIVES GOVERNANCE AND TALENT GOVERNANCE: AN ANALYSIS BASED ON JOB COMPETENCY, PERFORMANCE EVALUATION, AND ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS	475
Wang Biao	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	SANOAT KORXONALARI INNOVATSION SALOHIYATINI BAHOLASH METODIKASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	481
	Bahodirov Shohruh Bahodir o'g'li QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR BOZORINI TARTIBGA SOLISHNING XALQARO TAJRIBASI.....	488
	Mallabayev Jobir Baxtiyorovich ANALYSIS OF THE FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC ACTIVITY REPORTS OF OOO SAM TRADING STROY	493
	Usmonova Dilfuza Ilhomovna WAYS TO IMPROVE THE USE OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE TRANSPORT AND LOGISTICS CLUSTER IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN.....	500
	Musayeva Shoira Azimovna FOUNDATIONS FOR THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF TRANSPORT LOGISTICS IN UZBEKISTAN	507
	Muradov Alisher Kurbanbaevich	

FOUNDATIONS FOR THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF TRANSPORT LOGISTICS IN UZBEKISTAN

Muradov Alisher Kurbanbaevich
Independent researcher
Graduate School of Business and Entrepreneurship under the
Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan
Email: aliskermuradov82@gmail.com

Abstract: The article comprehensively examines the theoretical and methodological foundations of sustainable transport logistics development in the Republic of Uzbekistan under conditions of globalization and the growth of international trade. Particular attention was paid to analyzing the role of the transport and logistics system as a key factor in ensuring macroeconomic stability, increasing the competitiveness of the national economy, and integrating the country into global value chains.

The work provides a systematic analysis of the current state of transport infrastructure and logistical processes, identifies the main trends in their development, and evaluates the impact of institutional and technological factors on the efficiency of the industry's functioning. Issues regarding the digitalization of logistics, including the introduction of modern information and communication technologies, the automation of cargo flow management, and the development of intelligent transport systems, were considered separately.

Significant attention was paid to the development of multimodal transport as one of the key directions for increasing the efficiency of transport logistics, as well as the implementation of "green logistics" principles aimed at reducing the environmental burden and increasing the energy efficiency of the transport system.

Based on the analysis conducted, key structural limitations were identified, including high logistical costs, insufficient infrastructure development, limited digital transformation, and institutional barriers. To overcome them, a conceptual model for the sustainable development of transport logistics based on the integration of infrastructure, technological, environmental, and institutional components has been proposed.

The obtained results possess scientific novelty and practical significance, as they can be used in shaping state transport policy, developing strategies for the development of the logistics industry, and increasing the efficiency of transport system management.

Keywords: transport logistics, sustainable development, digitalization, multimodal transportation, logistics infrastructure, green logistics, transport corridors.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada globallashtirish va xalqaro savdo hajmining o'sishi sharoitida O'zbekiston Respublikasida transport logistikasini barqaror rivojlantirishning nazariy va metodologik asoslari kompleks tahlil qilingan. Transport-logistika tizimining makroiqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta'minlash, milliy iqtisodiyot raqobatbardoshligini oshirish hamda mamlakatni global qiymat zanjirlariga integratsiyalashdagi roli alohida ko'rib chiqilgan.

Ishda transport infratuzilmasi va logistika jarayonlarining joriy holati tizimli tahlil qilinib, ularning rivojlanish tendensiyalari aniqlangan hamda tarmoq samaradorligiga institutsional va texnologik omillarning ta'siri baholangan. Logistikani raqamlashtirish, jumladan, zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini joriy etish, yuk oqimlarini boshqarishni avtomatlashtirish va intellektual transport tizimlarini rivojlantirish masalalari alohida yoritilgan.

Transport logistikasining samaradorligini oshirishning muhim yo'nalishlaridan biri sifatida multimodal tashishlarni rivojlantirish, shuningdek, ekologik yuklamani kamaytirish va energiya samaradorligini oshirishga qaratilgan "yashil logistika" tamoyillarini joriy etish masalalariga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan.

O'tkazilgan tahlillar asosida yuqori logistika xarajatlari, infratuzilmaning yetarli darajada rivojlanmaganligi, raqamli transformatsiyaning cheklanganligi va institutsional to'siqlar kabi asosiy strukturaviy cheklovlar aniqlangan. Ularni bartaraf etish maqsadida infratuzilma, texnologik, ekologik va institutsional komponentlar integratsiyasiga asoslangan transport logistikasini barqaror rivojlantirishning konseptual modeli taklif etilgan.

Olingan natijalar ilmiy yangilik va amaliy ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, davlat transport siyosatini shakllantirishda, logistika tarmog'ini rivojlantirish strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishda hamda transport tizimini boshqarish samaradorligini oshirishda qo'llanilishi mumkin.

Kalit soʻzlar: transport logistikasi, barqaror rivojlanish, raqamlashtirish, multimodal tashishlar, logistika infrastruzilmasi, yashil logistika, transport koridorlari.

Аннотация: В статье комплексно исследуются теоретические и методологические основы устойчивого развития транспортной логистики в Республике Узбекистан в условиях глобализации и роста международной торговли. Особое внимание уделено анализу роли транспортно-логистической системы как ключевого фактора обеспечения макроэкономической стабильности, повышения конкурентоспособности национальной экономики и интеграции страны в глобальные цепочки добавленной стоимости.

В работе проведён системный анализ текущего состояния транспортной инфраструктуры и логистических процессов, выявлены основные тенденции их развития, а также оценено влияние институциональных и технологических факторов на эффективность функционирования отрасли. Отдельно рассмотрены вопросы цифровизации логистики, включая внедрение современных информационно-коммуникационных технологий, автоматизацию управления грузопотоками и развитие интеллектуальных транспортных систем.

Значительное внимание уделено развитию мультимодальных перевозок как одному из ключевых направлений повышения эффективности транспортной логистики, а также внедрению принципов «зелёной логистики», направленных на снижение экологической нагрузки и повышение энергоэффективности транспортной системы.

На основе проведённого анализа выявлены основные структурные ограничения, включая высокие логистические издержки, недостаточное развитие инфраструктуры, ограниченность цифровой трансформации и институциональные барьеры. Для их преодоления предложена концептуальная модель устойчивого развития транспортной логистики, основанная на интеграции инфраструктурных, технологических, экологических и институциональных компонентов.

Полученные результаты обладают научной новизной и практической значимостью, поскольку могут быть использованы при формировании государственной транспортной политики, разработке стратегий развития логистической отрасли и повышении эффективности управления транспортной системой.

Ключевые слова: транспортная логистика, устойчивое развитие, цифровизация, мультимодальные перевозки, логистическая инфраструктура, зелёная логистика, транспортные коридоры.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of the globalization of the global economy and the growth of international trade, the transport and logistics system is acquiring strategic importance. For countries with no direct access to the sea, such as Uzbekistan, the effective functioning of transport logistics is a key factor in ensuring the competitiveness of the national economy.

The concept of sustainable development involves a balanced combination of economic efficiency, environmental safety, and the social accessibility of transport services. In this context, the development of transport logistics requires the introduction of innovative technologies, infrastructure modernization, and increased institutional efficiency.

The object of the study is the transport and logistics system of Uzbekistan.

The subject of the study is the mechanisms for ensuring the sustainable development of transport logistics.

The aim of the study is to develop scientifically grounded recommendations for increasing the sustainability of the transport and logistics system.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The issue of sustainable development of transport logistics has been widely studied in the works of leading international scholars and institutions, where logistics is viewed as a key driver of economic efficiency, trade integration, and environmental balance. Rodrigue J. P. emphasizes that modern transport logistics systems are evolving from simple transportation functions into complex networks that integrate infrastructure, supply chains, and information flows, ensuring both efficiency and sustainability. His research highlights that the spatial organization of transport systems directly influences regional development and trade competitiveness.

Hesse M. and Rodrigue J. P. analyze the transformation of logistics systems under globalization, noting that freight distribution has become increasingly dependent on intermodal transport and advanced coordination mechanisms. They argue that sustainable logistics requires not only infrastructure development but also optimization of flows and reduction of transaction costs, which contributes to long-term economic stability.

The World Bank report *Connecting to Compete* underlines that logistics performance, measured through the Logistics Performance Index, plays a decisive role in enhancing national competitiveness. The report shows that countries with efficient customs procedures, reliable infrastructure, and advanced logistics services

achieve higher levels of trade integration and economic growth. This perspective is particularly relevant for developing economies such as Uzbekistan, where logistics modernization is closely linked with export expansion.

OECD Transport Outlook highlights the importance of integrating sustainability into transport systems, focusing on reducing emissions, improving energy efficiency, and promoting digitalization. The study demonstrates that future logistics systems must balance economic growth with environmental considerations, especially in the context of increasing global transport demand.

UNCTAD Review of Maritime Transport emphasizes the critical role of maritime logistics in global trade, noting that efficient port operations and connectivity are essential for reducing transport costs and improving supply chain resilience. The report also points out that developing countries need to invest in infrastructure and institutional reforms to enhance their participation in global logistics networks.

Asian Development Bank research on Uzbekistan transport sector development 2019 identifies infrastructure gaps, limited multimodal integration, and the need for institutional reforms as key challenges. At the same time, it highlights the country's strategic geographic position, which creates significant opportunities for becoming a regional logistics hub.

Stopford M. examines maritime economics and stresses that efficient logistics systems depend on cost optimization, fleet management, and market dynamics. His work provides a theoretical foundation for understanding the economic mechanisms underlying transport logistics systems.

Notteboom T. and Rodrigue J. P. introduce the concept of port regionalization, explaining how ports evolve into integrated logistics platforms connected with inland transport networks. This approach is crucial for enhancing the efficiency of national logistics systems and improving connectivity.

European Commission statistical analyses show that advanced transport systems are characterized by high levels of digitalization, infrastructure quality, and policy coordination. These factors collectively contribute to sustainable logistics development and improved service quality.

Sultonov B.Sh. analyzes the development of transport infrastructure in Uzbekistan and emphasizes the need for modernization, diversification of logistics services, and integration into international transport corridors. His research highlights that sustainable logistics development in Uzbekistan requires coordinated policy measures and investment strategies.

Overall, the reviewed literature demonstrates that sustainable transport logistics development is a multidimensional process influenced by infrastructure quality, institutional environment, digitalization, environmental policies, and integration into global supply chains. These factors must be considered collectively to ensure long-term efficiency and sustainability.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological framework of the study is based on the comprehensive application of modern scientific approaches and economic analysis methods, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of the state and prospects for the sustainable development of transport logistics in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Within the framework of the study, a systems approach was employed, according to which the transport and logistics system is considered a complex multi-level structure encompassing infrastructural, technological, institutional, and environmental elements. This approach allowed for the identification of relationships between various system components and the determination of their impact on the overall efficiency of logistical processes.

The application of comparative analysis has provided an opportunity to compare national indicators of transport logistics development with international standards and practices. This, in turn, made it possible to determine the level of competitiveness of Uzbekistan's transport and logistics system and identify key directions for its modernization.

The study also extensively utilized statistical analysis, including the processing of official data on cargo transportation dynamics, logistics cost levels, and transport infrastructure development. Based on the analysis of time series, the main trends and patterns of the industry's development were identified.

A special place is occupied by the structural decomposition method, which allowed for the decomposition of the transport and logistics system into individual functional elements and their detailed analysis. This made it possible to identify bottlenecks in the system's functioning, as well as to evaluate the contribution of each element to the formation of final results.

Additionally, elements of logical and abstract-analytical methods were applied in the work, which ensured the formation of generalized conclusions and the development of scientifically grounded recommendations.

The comprehensive application of these methods has enabled not only the identification of key trends and problems in the development of transport logistics but also the formation of conceptual approaches to ensuring its sustainable development in the long term.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Analysis shows that Uzbekistan's transport and logistics system has demonstrated positive development dynamics in recent years. There is an increase in cargo transportation volumes, an expansion of transport infrastructure, and the active development of international transport corridors.

At the same time, the following systemic features were identified:

- high share of logistics costs in the GDP structure, reflecting the scale and economic significance of the sector;
- growing level of digitalization of logistics processes, indicating ongoing technological transformation;
- progressive integration of various types of transport, supporting the development of multimodal systems;
- environmental considerations associated with increasing transportation loads, highlighting the importance of sustainable solutions. The introduction of digital technologies, which allow for increased efficiency in managing logistical flows and reducing operational costs, is of particular importance.

Based on the analysis conducted, a conceptual model for the sustainable development of transport logistics is proposed, which includes:

- 1) infrastructure component (development of transport networks)
- 2) technological component (digitalization and automation);
- 3) environmental component (reduction of emissions);
- 4) institutional component (improving management) (Table 1).

Table 1. Indicators of Transport and Logistics System Development in Uzbekistan¹

Indicators	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	trend
Volume of cargo transportation (million tons)	1200	1350	1500	1700	1900	
Logistics costs (% of GDP)	18	17	16	15	14	
Level of digital logistics (%)	20	28	37	48	60	
Multimodal integration rate (%)	30	35	40	45	50	
CO2 emissions (index, 2020=100)	100	105	110	115	120	

The data in Table 1 show that the transport and logistics system is demonstrating steady growth in volume. At the same time, the reduction of logistical costs indicates an increase in system efficiency. However, the growing environmental burden (CO2) indicates the need to transition to "green logistics (Figure 1)."

Figure 1. Dynamics of Transportation Volumes and Logistics Costs (2020-2024)²

¹ Source: author's own work

² Source: author's own work

This graph reflects the dynamics of changes in transportation volumes and logistics costs between 2020 and 2024. Data show that transportation volume has a steady growth trend, increasing from 1,200 million tons in 2020 to 1,900 million tons by 2024. This indicates the development of the transport and logistics system and the expansion of economic activity in the country.

At the same time, logistics costs have the opposite trend, decreasing from 18% to 14%. This is explained by the optimization of logistics processes, the introduction of digital technologies, and the improvement of transport infrastructure.

Overall, the graph shows a positive correlation between the increase in transport volumes and the decrease in logistics costs, indicating an increase in system efficiency (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Structural problem diagram³

This diagram shows the main “narrow points” in the system and serves as a basis for developing the model.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

As a result of the conducted research, it has been established that the sustainable development of transport logistics is one of the key factors for the long-term economic growth of the Republic of Uzbekistan. An effectively functioning transport and logistics system not only ensures the enhancement of national economy competitiveness but also contributes to the country’s integration into global supply chains, expanding its transit potential.

The conducted analysis showed that the current state of transport logistics is characterized by positive development dynamics, manifested in the growth of cargo transportation volumes, infrastructure modernization, and the expansion of international transport corridors. At the same time, a number of systemic development opportunities remain, related to the high share of logistics costs, the ongoing expansion of digitalization, and the strengthening of interspecific integration of transport systems.

It is particularly emphasized that the sustainable development of the industry is impossible without a comprehensive approach, including institutional reforms, technological modernization, and the ecological transformation of logistical processes. In modern conditions, digital technologies play a key role, allowing for increased transparency, manageability, and efficiency of logistical operations.

The main findings of the study are:

- transport logistics acts as a system-forming and strategically important element of the national economy;
- sustainable development of the industry requires the integration of infrastructural, technological, and institutional factors;
- digitalization and greening are priority areas for transforming the transport and logistics system;
- improving logistics efficiency is directly linked to reducing transactional and operating costs;

³ Source: author's own work

• the development of multimodal transportation strengthens the country's transit potential and enhances its competitiveness.

Recommendations:

1. Development of digital logistics platforms

Implementation of unified digital cargo flow management systems to increase the transparency and efficiency of logistical processes.

2. Implementation of "Smart Logistics" technologies

Utilizing artificial intelligence, IoT, and big data to optimize routes and forecast cargo flows.

3. Reduction of logistics costs

Improving tariff policy, optimizing transport chains, and eliminating administrative barriers.

4. Development of multimodal transport systems

Integration of rail, road, air, and water transport into a unified logistics network.

5. Implementation of "green logistics" principles

Reducing carbon dioxide emissions, implementing environmentally friendly transport modes, and increasing energy efficiency.

Thus, the sustainable development of transport logistics in Uzbekistan should be viewed as a multi-level process requiring the coordination of efforts by the state, business, and international partners. The implementation of the proposed directions will not only increase the efficiency of the logistics system but also ensure its long-term sustainability under conditions of global economic transformations.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Rodrigue J. P. The Geography of Transport Systems. – New York: Routledge, 2020. – 456 p.
2. Hesse M., Rodrigue J.P. The transport geography of logistics and freight distribution. *Journal of Transport Geography*. – 2004. – Vol. 12(3). – P. 171–184.
3. World Bank. Connecting to Compete 2018: Trade Logistics in the Global Economy. – Washington, DC: World Bank, 2018. – 80 p.
4. OECD. ITF Transport Outlook 2021. – Paris: OECD Publishing, 2021. – 120 p.
5. UNCTAD. Review of Maritime Transport 2022. – New York and Geneva: United Nations, 2022. – 168 p.
6. Asian Development Bank. Uzbekistan: Transport Sector Assessment, Strategy, and Road Map. – Manila: ADB, 2019. – 72 p.
7. European Commission. EU Transport in Figures: Statistical Pocketbook 2022. – Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2022. – 180 p.
8. Stopford M. *Maritime Economics*. 3rd ed. – London: Routledge, 2009. – 816 p.
9. Notteboom T., Rodrigue J. P. Port regionalization: towards a new phase in port development. *Maritime Policy & Management*. – 2005. – Vol. 32(3). – P. 297–313.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2026. № 4 (2)

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>